

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Technology integration in educational leadership in public elementary schools of tabaco city division

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ABSTRACT

This study examines technology integration in school leadership among 40 public elementary schools in SDO-Tabaco City for the school year 2023–2024. It identifies the technologies used, their impact on leadership domains, challenges encountered, and a proposed management plan.

Findings reveal four key technologies in educational leadership: Learners' Information Systems, Communication Platforms, Virtual Meeting Platforms, and Online Collaboration Tools. School heads frequently integrate technology across five leadership domains, with leading strategically showing the highest usage. The benefits of technology include improved communication, efficiency, remote accessibility, and enhanced innovation. However, major challenges include budget constraints, limited access, inadequate infrastructure, privacy concerns, and insufficient training.

To address these challenges, the study presents a structured plan outlining objective, activities, responsible personnel, and expected outcomes. It recommends further research on technology's role in educational leadership, increased technical assistance, and the sharing of best practices to strengthen integration.

Conclusively, the study underscores the importance of technology in school leadership, noting its positive influence while highlighting critical areas for improvement. Recommendations aim to elevate technology usage from high to very high, ensuring seamless integration into school leadership functions.

Potential areas for further study include case analyses on technology in leadership, resource management, and the formulation of a model for effective technology-driven school leadership.

Keywords: Leadership; Technology Integration; Seamless Integration; Tabaco City

1. Introduction

This is descriptive survey research among the forty public elementary schools in SDO-Tabaco City for the school year 2023 – 2024, which are the respondents of this study. It determined the technology integration in school leadership of the public elementary schools in Tabaco City Division. Specifically, it answered the following sub-problems: (1) What are the technologies integrated in educational leadership?; (2) What is the level of influence of technology integration in school leadership along (a) leading strategically, (b) managing resources, (c) focusing in teaching and learning, (d) developing self and others, and (e) building connection?; (3) What are the effects of technology integration to school leadership?;(4) What are the challenges encountered in technology integration in school leadership?; and (5) What management plan may be proposed to address the problem?

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The school heads vary in age, which ranges from early thirties to late fifties. They also differ in gender preferences, but most of them are female. They also differ in the number of years as school heads. They also differ in their Plantilla Positions – Head Teachers, Teacher-In-Charge, Master Teachers, Principal 1, 2, and 3. Generally, the forty public elementary school heads in SDO-Tabaco City share the same practices and concerns, along with technology integration as part of their duties and functions.

As an outcome of the study, the researcher was able to come up with a plan of action on how to address the difficulties encountered by the school heads in using technology in their line of work. It was presented in the form of a table, which included the objectives, activities, time frame, persons responsible, and expected outcome. The researcher hopes that the school heads will be able to make use of this plan to address the difficulties they encounter.

2. Findings

2.1. After the data had been collected, recorded, and organized, the researcher found the following facts

There were only four technologies integrated into Educational Leadership. These were Learners' Information Systems, Communication Platforms, Virtual Meeting Platforms, and Online Collaboration Tools.

For the level of technology integration, the researcher presented a five-point scale with corresponding adjectival descriptions of always, often, sometimes, rarely, and never, respectively. The researcher found out that on average, the school heads are often using technology integration in their five key result areas (KRA). Each KRA obtained the following results based on the accomplished research instruments:

- They were always using technology integration along with leading strategically, which obtained an average weighted mean of 4.21. This obtained the highest average weighted mean among the five key result areas.
- They were often using technology integration along the KRA of school heads on managing resources, which obtained an average weighted mean of 4.08.
- They were also often using technology integration along with focusing on teaching and learning, which got an average weighted mean of 3.86.
- They were often using technology integration along with the roles of school heads on developing self and others.
- They were often using technology integration along the fifth KRA on building connections, which obtained an average weighted mean of 4.18.

Along the third sub-problem, the researcher was able to find out that technology integration has the following effects on school leadership: (1) makes communication easier; (2) gathers information faster; (3) transmits required documents quicker; (4) develops innovation and creativity; (5) makes the work more efficient; (6) improves communication; (7) enhances efficiency and productivity at work; (8) allows to work remotely; (9) easy access to information; and (10) allows flexible learning environment.

From the answers of the respondents, the researcher was able to find out the top five problems along technology integration. These were as follows: (1) budget constraints; (2) limited accessibility; (3) inadequate infrastructure; (4) privacy issues; and (5) insufficient training.

As an outcome of the study, the researcher came up with a plan of action to address the problems encountered by the school heads, along with technology integration, which comes in the form of a table.

3. Conclusion

3.1. In light of the findings, the researcher was able to derive the following conclusions

- *Learners' Information System, Communication Platforms, Virtual Meeting Platforms, and Online Collaboration Tools* are the four technologies integrated into the work of school heads as leaders and managers.

- Along the five key result areas (KRAs) of the school heads, it was concluded that school leaders in SDO-Tabaco City generally have a high level of technology integration.
- There were ten effects of technology integration which include the following: (1) *makes communication easier*; (2) *gathers information faster*; (3) *transmits required documents quicker*; (4) *develops innovation and creativity*; (5) *makes the work more efficient*; (6) *improves communication*; (7) *enhances efficiency and productivity at work*; (8) *allows to work remotely*; (9) *easy access to information*; and (10) *allows flexible learning environment*.
- These were the top five problems along technology integration: (1) *budget constraints*; (2) *limited accessibility*; (3) *inadequate infrastructures*; (4) *privacy issues*; and (5) *insufficient training*.
- A management plan to address the problems the school heads encountered, along with technology integration in their duties and functions as heads of schools was crafted.

Recommendations

- Considering the conclusions, the researcher presents the following recommendations:
- More in-depth research should be undertaken by interested researchers so that they can dig deeper into the various technologies integrated into the roles of school heads using qualitative research methods.
- Technical Assistance will be provided among the school heads to enhance the integration of various technologies in their duties and functions, and raise the technology integration from high to very high.
- There were positive effects of technology integration along the KRAs of school heads, but interested researchers may dig deeper into how these effects are perceived and appreciated in the workplace.
- The top five problems encountered by the school heads along with technology integration should be addressed by providing technical assistance by the Division ITO or sharing of schools' good practices, particularly the techie ones.
- The management plan crafted by the researcher can be applied in the schools so that the challenges can be addressed and make technology integration seamless.

Areas for Further Study

The following areas are recommended for further research

- Technology Integration in Leadership and Management: A Case Study
- Technology Integration as Used in Managing School Resources
- Technology Integration in School: Basis for a Model School Head

References

- [1] ¹DepEd Order No. 68 series 2010. Revised Guidelines on the Implementation of the Department of Education Computerization Program
- [2] ²Republic Act 10844 Department of Information and Communications Technology Act of 2015 <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2016/05/23/republic-act-no-10844/#:~:text=AN%20ACT%20CREATING%20THE%20DEPARTMENT,THEREFOR%2C%20AND%20FOR%20OTHER%20PURPOSES>
- [3] Dictionary.com. Definition of Technology. Retrieved on May 19, 2024. Retrieved from: <https://www.dictionary.com>
- [4] Cambridge University Press and Assessment. Definition of Integration. Retrieved on May 5, 2024 from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org>
- [5] Webster Dictionary. Definition of Technology Integration. Retrieved from <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/practices>.
- [6] Dictionary.com. Definition of School Leadership Retrieved on May 5, 2024. Retrieved from: <https://www.dictionary.com>
- [7] Python dictionaries. Definition of Schools. Retrieved on May 5, 2024 from https://www.w3schools.com/python/python_dictionaries.asp
- [8] Cambridge.com. Definition of Management. Retrieved on May 5, 2024. Retrieved from: <https://www.dictionary.com>

- [9] Law Insider. Definition of School Management. Retrieved on May 20, 2024 from <https://www.lawinsider.com>
- [10] Cambridge University Press and Assessment. Definition of Leading Strategically. Retrieved on May 5, 2024 from <https://dictionary.cambridge.org>
- [11] Dictionary.Com. Definition of Efficiency. Retrieved on May 5, 2024 from <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/english-dictionary>
- [12] Dictionary.Com. Definition of Innovation. Retrieved on May 15, 2024 from <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/english-dictionary>
- [13] Python Dictionaries. Definition of Practices. Retrieved on May 5, 2024 from https://www.w3schools.com/python/python_dictionaries.asp
- [14] Cambridge.com. Definition of Professional Development. Retrieved on May 5, 2024. Retrieved from: <https://www.dictionary.com>